

UNSTEADY FLOW SIMULATION IN A THREE STAGE TURBINE WITH CAVITIES USING TIME AND FREQUENCY DOMAIN METHODS

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ABSTRACT

The accurate prediction of turbomachinery performance and unsteady flow phenomena requires the consideration of secondary geometrical features such as air-seal cavities, which significantly influence both global and local flow characteristics. This study focuses on a large-scale, industrially relevant low-pressure turbine rig comprising six blade rows, including a turning mid-turbine frame and multiple secondary cavities, representative of modern engine configurations. The importance of unsteady simulation methods is demonstrated for improving the prediction of overall performance metrics, such as isentropic efficiency, as well as local phenomena, including temperature distribution accuracy. To address the high computational cost of conventional time-domain simulations based on dual-time stepping, a frequency-domain approach using the Harmonic Balance method has been implemented and assessed within our computation fluid dynamics solver. The Harmonic Balance method is validated against reference time-domain simulations, showing a substantial reduction in computational cost while maintaining sufficient accuracy for both global performance and unsteady pressure amplitudes on a selected blade row. Differences between the two approaches are analyzed and attributed to the limited frequency content in the Harmonic Balance setup, particularly regarding clocking and indexing effects between blade rows. These findings highlight the potential of the Harmonic Balance method as an efficient alternative for unsteady turbomachinery simulations in industrial design processes.

Keywords: Turbine Aerodynamics, Cavities, Harmonic Balance, URANS, Radial Mixing

Nomenclature

Abbreviations

EO	Engine order
BPF	Blade Passing Frequency
HB	Harmonic Balance
IBPA	Inter-blade Phase Angle [°]
NRBC	Non-reflecting Boundary Condition
ps	pressure side
ss	suction side
TD	Time Domain
TMTF	Turning mid-turbine frame
VPF	Vane Passing Frequency

Greek Letters

η	Efficiency
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Roman Letters

f	Frequency [Hz]
m	Circumferential wave number [-]
N_B	Number of blades [-]
p	Pressure [Pa]
r	Radius [m]
s/c	Relative chord length [-]
t	Time [s]
T_{rev}	Time normalized by segment passing period

Subscripts and Superscripts

amp	Amplitude
is	Isentropic
max	Maximum
nrm	Normalized value
R, S	Rotor, Stator
rel	relative

1 INTRODUCTION

Accurate prediction of unsteady flow phenomena in low-pressure turbines (LPTs) remains a critical challenge in turbomachinery design. Conventional steady-state Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations are widely used in industry due to their robustness and relatively low computational cost. However, these approaches often fail to resolve key flow features, particularly the radial mixing of wake structures, because of the inherent limitations of the mixing plane interface. This interface performs circumferential averaging at rotor-stator boundaries, which effectively suppresses the transport of unsteady structures between blade rows.

To capture these interactions more accurately, unsteady time-domain URANS simulations using a dual-time stepping approach are widely adopted in industrial practice. These simulations employ sliding-mesh interfaces that exchange flow variables without circumferential averaging, enabling the propagation of wakes and secondary flow structures through the entire machine. While URANS does not represent the highest-fidelity approach — methods such as Large Eddy Simulation (LES) or even Direct Numerical Simulation (DNS) offer superior accuracy — these methods remain computationally prohibitive for high-Reynolds-number, multi-stage configurations. Consequently, time-domain URANS serves as the practical reference standard for large-scale industrial applications, despite its significant computational cost.

The importance of unsteady effects for performance prediction has been demonstrated in several studies. Praisner et al. [1] reported differences in isentropic efficiency of approximately 0.8% between steady and unsteady simulations in axial-flow turbomachinery, primarily due to wake mixing. Hammer et al. [2] further highlighted that mixing losses constitute a major contribution in detailed loss decompositions following Denton’s methodology [3]. These findings underline the necessity of unsteady modeling for accurate performance and loss predictions.

Frequency-domain methods, such as the Harmonic Balance (HB) approach, offer a computationally efficient alternative by resolving only the most important frequency content of the unsteady flow. This significantly reduces the number of degrees of freedom compared to time-domain simulations. However, the application of HB to complex multi-stage turbines — especially those including secondary features such as inner and outer air-seal cavities — remains limited and underexplored. These cavities introduce additional interactions and flow recirculation zones, which pose challenges for both modeling and numerical stability.

In previous work, a novel sliding-mesh interface tailored for HB simulations was introduced by Geiser et al. [4]. The method was successfully applied to a single-stage compressor rotor with slot-type casing treatments and later extended to a 1.5-stage academic turbine including cavity flows [5, 6]. Building on these foundations, the present study investigates a more complex and

industrially relevant configuration: a three-stage low-pressure turbine representative of modern aero-engine architectures. The objectives are to assess (i) the impact of secondary air-seal cavities on global and local flow characteristics, (ii) the differences between steady and unsteady modeling approaches, and (iii) the capability of the HB method to reproduce unsteady phenomena at significantly reduced computational cost.

2 METHODOLOGIES

All simulations are performed using the turbomachinery research and design code TRACE, developed by the German Aerospace Center (DLR) and MTU Aero Engines AG [7]. TRACE solves the three-dimensional compressible Favre-averaged Navier-Stokes equations using a density-based finite volume method. Although the code supports both structured and unstructured multi-block meshes, only structured grids are employed in this study. Convective fluxes are discretized using Roe’s approximate Riemann solver with a second-order MUSCL extrapolation for spatial accuracy [8]. To ensure numerical stability and suppress spurious oscillations near discontinuities, a Van Albada limiter is applied [9]. Viscous fluxes are computed using a central difference scheme with mixed derivative terms. Turbulence effects are modeled using the two-equation eddy viscosity model proposed by [10], including the Kato-Laundar modification to address the stagnation point anomaly [11].

2.1 Interface Treatment

The computational domain consists of multiple blade rows, which require appropriate coupling strategies at the interfaces between adjacent components. Several different approaches are available in TRACE:

Mixing Plane Approach in Steady-State For steady-state simulations, the mixing plane method is employed. This approach circumferentially averages flow quantities on radial bands at the interface, effectively removing unsteady fluctuations. As a result, wake-structures and other circumferential non-uniformities are mixed out, limiting the accuracy of down- and upstream predictions.

Mixing Plane Approach in Harmonic Balance In the context of HB simulations, the interface treatment is conceptually based on the mixing-plane approach but extended to preserve unsteady information. Instead of performing a circumferential averaging, the HB method exchanges the Fourier coefficients of the circumferential modes across the interface for each radial band. These coefficients represent the harmonic content of the flow field in the frequency domain, allowing the method to retain non-uniformities such as wakes and potential fields without

mixing them out.

An important consequence of this approach is that only a single-passage model per blade row is required, as the circumferential variation is reconstructed from the harmonic content. This significantly reduces the computational cost compared to full-annulus or large-sector time-domain simulations, while still capturing the dominant unsteady interactions between blade rows.

Sliding-Mesh Approach For time-domain unsteady simulations, TRACE employs a sliding-mesh interface to couple adjacent blade rows [12]. This method allows relative motion between components without requiring grid point matching across the interface. Flow variables are interpolated and exchanged between the two sides, enabling the transport of wakes and other unsteady features across domains.

A key requirement for this approach is that the pitch on both sides of the interface must be identical. This condition is typically achieved by duplicating blade passages until a common pitch segment is formed. In many practical configurations however, blade counts are chosen as prime numbers to avoid resonant excitations, which means that achieving pitch matching often requires simulating the full annulus. Consequently, the computational cost can increase significantly. While phase-lag techniques [13–15] exist to reduce the domain size, their applicability in the time domain is limited, particularly for capturing long-range interactions such as clocking and indexing effects.

In the HB method, a similar interpolation strategy is applied, but only at a discrete set of sampling points in time. At the beginning of each simulation, these sampling points are defined based on the selected harmonics according to [4]. The solution is then transformed between the frequency and time domains, and the interface exchange operates analogously to the time-domain approach at these sampling points. Due to the strong formulation of an interblade phase angle between different domains, the interface also functions with a different pitch on both sides. This means that it is sufficient to calculate only one passage per row in HB. This concept was first introduced by [16] and recently improved for efficient application in the HB solver [4]. This approach enables the accurate transfer of unsteady content across blade rows while maintaining the computational efficiency of the frequency-domain formulation.

We can see the different behavior of interface approaches in steady simulations (Fig. 1a) and unsteady simulations in the HB method (Fig. 1b). The transient results show long wakes that are not mixed out. Between the sliding-mesh approach in the time-domain (Fig. 1c) and the mixing plane approach in HB is a very good agreement.

2.2 Dual-time stepping method

The URANS simulations in the time domain are conducted using an implicit Euler backward time discretization scheme. Be-

cause of its implicit formulation, a CFL number of 200 can be applied. To capture also the harmonics of the highest engine orders, generated by the row with the highest blade count, we have chosen to resolve one blade passing period with 35 time steps. Periodic convergence is assessed by monitoring the local flow values at several locations in the main flow and within the cavities. These signals are analyzed using a Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) over two segment passing periods, similar to the work of [17]. Starting from a steady-state initial solution, the unsteady time-domain simulations converged after 7 segment passing periods.

2.3 Harmonic Balance

The HB solver within TRACE has proven to be highly effective in simulating unsteady flow fields, frequently offering a more efficient alternative to conventional time-domain methods in various applications [18]. It solves the quasi-steady RANS equations for a given set of solution harmonics using an alternating time and frequency domain algorithm. This approach allows the general transport equations, as well as boundary conditions, to be consistently applied in both solvers. The consistency between these two modes is unique to the HB method and enables a direct and reliable comparison between the conventional time-domain solver and the HB solver. The HB calculations have been initialized by a converged steady RANS solution. Because of convergence issues, the HB calculation with unsteady flow predictions in the cavities has been initialized by the first HB results with steady cavity flows but unsteady main flow. To incorporate the fluctuations of the turbulent model quantities in a numerically stable manner, a Lanczos filter method is applied in all HB calculations [19]. A CFL number of five was employed for the pseudo-time step, as using higher values resulted in a destabilization of the solver. All sliding mesh interfaces use the latest implementation by [4] for both simulation types in time and frequency domain. First successful applications of this interface have been presented by [5]. Especially for the simulation of multi-stage turbomachinery, the effects of clocking and indexing between domains with the same frame of reference is important to consider. The first stator of the assessed LPT configuration is realised as combined mid-center frame and turning stator. Due to its high chord length compared to the remaining rows, its impact is considered in all assessed blade and vane rows. In Stator 2 this effect is addressed by an harmonic set with frequency zero and an IBPA between TMTF and Stator 2. This approach is successfully shown in the work of [20].

In HB simulations, the solution is represented by a finite set of harmonics in the frequency domain. Each computational domain is associated with one or more harmonic sets. A harmonic set is defined by a base frequency ω_i , a list of higher harmonics of these basefrequency and the corresponding inter-blade phase angles (IBPAs) for each frequency.

FIGURE 1: ENTROPY FIELD IN THE LAST TWO ROWS. THE LEGEND APPLIES TO ALL SUBFIGURES.

3 TEST CASE

This study is based on the simulation of a low pressure turbine rig representative of modern aircraft applications. The configuration includes six blade rows — one turning mid turbine frame at the inlet, three rotors, and two stators — along with secondary air-seal cavities at hub and casing sides. A schematic of the geometry is shown in Fig. 2. Blade 2 is highlighted in red, as it is analyzed in detail in the results section with respect to unsteady pressure amplitudes. Additionally, the location of the radial temperature analysis is indicated by a red dashed line between Stator 3 and Rotor 3. The number of blades B_i and vanes V_i are all multiple of two, so the model can be calculated on a 180 deg model in the time domain. Boundary conditions are

FIGURE 2: MERIDIONAL VIEW OF THE LOW-PRESSURE TURBINE RIG, INCLUDING MAIN FLOW PATH AND SECONDARY CAVITIES.

imposed by prescribing radial profiles of total pressure p_t , total temperature T_t , as well as inflow angles for the flow velocity. Turbulence boundary conditions are defined by associated values for turbulence intensity Tu and turbulence length scale l_s . The outlet static pressure is adjusted, so that the total pressure ratio between machine inlet and outlet matches the measured value. The total

temperature at the inlet is moderately low and the inflow mach number remains subsonic across the span. The Reynolds number based on the rotor inlet conditions is on the order of 10^5 , typical for low-pressure turbines.

To assess the influence of secondary features, additional steady and unsteady simulations were conducted on a simplified configuration without cavities and endwall contouring. For these cases, boundary conditions were adapted to maintain the same operating point and pressure ratio as the reference configuration.

3.1 NUMERICAL SETUP

Mesh and Grid Resolution The computational mesh is designed to accurately resolve the main flow path and secondary features such as cavities. In the primary flow regions, the grid resolution is sufficiently fine to fully resolve the viscous sub-layer of the boundary layer, and therefore wall functions are not required. Inside the cavities, wall functions are applied for turbulence modeling, as near-wall resolution is of secondary importance in these regions compared to the main flow. The mesh within the cavities is coupled to the primary flow domain via sliding-mesh interfaces, enabling unsteady flow interaction.

A γ - Re_θ transition model based on [21], which solves two additional transport equations for the transitional model quantities, is applied to the main flow path to account for laminar-to-turbulent transition effects, whereas no transition modeling is implemented within the cavities.

Boundary Conditions and Operating Point All simulations, steady and unsteady, are performed at the same operating point, defined by identical inlet profiles and back pressure. For simplified configurations without cavities and EWC, the boundary conditions are adjusted to match the overall pressure ratio of the reference case. Non-reflecting boundary conditions formulated in the frequency domain are applied at both inlet and outlet boundaries across all simulations. This approach is compatible with both the time-domain and Harmonic Balance solvers, ensuring consistency in the treatment of wave reflections and enabling a fair comparison between the two methods [22, 23].

Simulation Matrix Six different configurations are considered in this study. The selection of the six configurations aims to systematically assess the influence of cavity geometry and unsteady modeling on turbine performance. First, two configurations without cavities and two with cavities are included to quantify the impact of secondary air-seal cavities on the main flow and global performance metrics under both steady and unsteady conditions. For the cavity cases, two additional HB configurations are considered to evaluate the feasibility of HB in multi-stage turbines with inner and outer air-seal cavities. One HB setup resolves only the time-averaged flow inside the cavities, while the other applies the same harmonic sets within the cavities as in the main flow path, representing a more advanced modeling approach. Finally, the most computationally expensive configuration — the unsteady TD simulation with cavities — serves as the reference case for all comparisons.

RANS, woCav: Steady RANS simulation without cavities and endwall contouring (EWC).

URANS-TD, woCav: Unsteady time-domain simulation without cavities and EWC.

RANS: Steady RANS simulation with cavities and EWC.

URANS-HB, steadyCav: Unsteady Harmonic Balance simulation with time-averaged cavities.

URANS-HB: Unsteady Harmonic Balance simulation with unsteady cavities.

URANS-TD: Unsteady time-domain simulation with cavities and EWC (reference).

Harmonic Balance Setup For HB simulations, four harmonics of neighboring blade rows are considered downstream and three upstream to capture the dominant interaction effects. Due to the higher axial chord length and larger pitch size of the TMTF, its influence is resolved using eight harmonics in this research. Additional clocking sets are included in Rotor 1, Stator 2, and Rotor 2 to account for interaction effects between multiple blade rows. The harmonic sets for each domain are summarized in Table 1. When cavities are resolved unsteadily, the same harmonic sets as in the adjacent main flow domain are applied.

4 RESULTS

This section presents the key findings of the study, focusing on the influence of secondary air-seal cavities and unsteady flow modeling on the aerodynamic performance and flow field characteristics of the low-pressure turbine configuration. The results are structured into three parts: (i) global machine performance metrics, (ii) time-averaged radial temperature profiles, and (iii) unsteady pressure amplitudes on blade row 2. Comparisons are made between steady and unsteady approaches, as well as between time-domain and frequency-domain methods, to

TABLE 1: HARMONIC SETS FOR EACH DOMAIN IN THE MAIN FLOW AND THEIR ASSOCIATED BASE FREQUENCIES.

Domain	Base frequency	Harmonics
TMTF	BPF_{R1}	0 1 2 3
Rotor 1	VPF_{TMTF}	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8
	VPF_{S1}	0 1 2 3
Stator 2	BPF_{R1}	0 1 2 3 4
	BPF_{R2}	0 1 2 3
	0	0 1 2 3 4 5 6 7
Rotor 2	VPF_{S2}	0 1 2 3 4
	VPF_{S3}	0 1 2 3
	VPF_{TMTF}	0 1 2 3 4
Stator 3	BPF_{R2}	0 1 2 3 4
	BPF_{R3}	0 1 2 3
Rotor 3	VPF_{S3}	0 1 2 3 4

assess both accuracy and computational efficiency.

4.1 Global machine performance

Figure 3 presents a horizontal bar plot showing the difference in isentropic efficiency between each CFD setup and the reference case. The x-axis represents the efficiency deviation, while the y-axis lists the six simulation configurations. Bars corresponding to setups without cavities are indicated by hatching, whereas solid gray bars denote configurations that include cavities. The isentropic efficiency is computed from integral values at the inlet and outlet planes of the entire machine.

The results highlight two major trends. First, the influence of cavity geometry is significant: configurations that exclude cavities consistently overpredict isentropic efficiency compared to the reference case. This discrepancy underscores the necessity of incorporating secondary air-seal cavities in high-fidelity turbine simulations, as their omission leads to a completely different representation of secondary flow losses.

Second, the role of unsteady modeling becomes evident when comparing steady-state and time-resolved approaches. Independent of geometric fidelity, steady-state simulations exhibit noticeable deviations from unsteady methods. Both the time domain and HB approaches predict lower efficiencies, indicating

FIGURE 3: TIME-AVERAGED ISENTROPIC EFFICIENCY ACROSS THE ENTIRE MACHINE.

that unsteady phenomena — such as wake transport and vortex interactions — introduce additional losses not captured by the mixing plane method. The HB simulations demonstrate strong agreement with the TD reference results. The initial HB configuration with steady cavity modeling shows a deviation of only 0.14%, while the setup with unsteady cavities improves this further to just 0.09%. These results confirm that the HB method can accurately reproduce global performance metrics, while offering a significantly lower computational cost, as detailed in Table 2.

4.2 Radial Mixing in Temperature

The time-averaged radial profiles of total temperature upstream of the last rotor row area shown in Fig. 4. The results reveal a pronounced influence of secondary air-seal cavities on the radial distribution. Neglecting the cavities leads to significant deviations, particularly near the shroud, where differences of approximately 8 K are observed between configurations with and without cavities. This highlights the role of cavity-induced mixing in shaping the endwall flow structures.

Near the hub, the inclusion of cavities results in a temperature increase of about 2 K. For these cases, the HB results closely match the steady-state solution, whereas the TD simulation predicts a slightly higher temperature level, with a bulk difference approximately 2 K that is not fully captured by HB.

At mid-span, steady state simulations underpredict the total temperature by up to 2 K compared to unsteady approaches. This discrepancy reflects the inability of the mixing plane method to capture unsteady transport mechanisms such as wake convection and vortex migration. In contrast, both unsteady methods — TD and HB — show very good agreement in this region, confirming that the HB method can reproduce the dominant unsteady effects with high fidelity.

Minor discrepancies near the hub and shroud between HB and TD may be related to limited frequency content in the HB

FIGURE 4: TIME-AVERAGED RADIAL DISTRIBUTION OF TOTAL TEMPERATURE UPSTREAM OF THE LAST ROTOR ROW.

setups. However, further analysis would be required to confirm this hypothesis.

4.3 Unsteady Pressure on Blade 2

Figure 5 presents contour plots of pressure amplitudes on the pressure and suction sides of Blade 2 for all unsteady simulations. The colormap corresponds to the vane passing frequency (VPF) of the second stator row located upstream of Blade 2.

The highest amplitudes are observed on the suction side near the leading edge at approximately 20–30% channel height, as well as at the blade tip. These regions are associated with strong unsteady forcing due to upstream wake interactions. On the pressure side, the amplitude distribution remains relatively uniform, and no significant changes are observed between the different configurations.

For aeroelastic considerations, the mid-span and tip regions are of particular interest because the hub region is structurally thicker and less susceptible to vibration. Therefore, detailed profiles are evaluated at 50% and 95% blade height to capture the most critical regions for aeroelastic response. These two spanwise positions are indicated by purple lines in Figure 5.

At mid-span, the results of the TD simulation without cavities (a) are in good agreement with both HB configurations (b,c) and the TD reference case with cavities (d). This indicates that the HB method captures the dominant unsteady excitation mechanisms with sufficient accuracy. The influence of cavities is primarily confined to the hub and shroud regions, where local amplitude variations are observed. At the blade tip on the suction

side, a distinct circular high-amplitude region appears only in the configurations with cavities, and this feature is consistently resolved by both HB and TD simulations.

Blade Surface Amplitude Profiles. To quantify these observations, Figures 6a and 6b show the pressure amplitude distributions along the blade surface at 50% and 95% channel height, respectively. At mid-span (Fig. 6a), all methods exhibit very good agreement on both pressure and suction sides, except near the trailing edge on the suction side, where HB predicts slightly lower amplitudes than TD. The presence of cavities has only a minor influence at this span location.

At 95% channel height (Fig. 6b), the differences between configurations become more pronounced. The largest deviations occur around 20% relative chord on the suction side, where the interaction with the cavity appears to increase the pressure amplitudes at the VPF. Furthermore, the HB results show noticeable differences depending on whether the cavity is treated as steady or unsteady. When unsteady cavities are resolved, the pressure amplitudes increase on the pressure side near the trailing edge, suggesting that disturbances can propagate through the cavity, bypass the blade row, and re-enter the main flow downstream of Blade 2.

A more detailed analysis of the TD reference simulation across all blades in the 180° sector reveals a mode corresponding to a nodal diameter of two. This suggests clocking effects between Blade 1 and Blade 2, which are not represented in the HB simulations due to the limited frequency content. Including additional harmonics could capture these effects, but this would significantly increase computational cost. Moreover, such frequencies are not known a priori and were only identified through post-processing of the TD results.

Computational Cost and Mesh Statistics The mesh size and computational cost for each simulation are summarized in Table 2. All values are normalized by the steady RANS configuration without cavities, which serves as the baseline for comparison.

Due to the single-passage modeling in HB simulations, the mesh size is significantly smaller compared to TD simulations, which require a 180 deg sector. For the full machine, this results in approximately 33 times more cells in the TD cases. The inclusion of cavities increases the total cell count by about 66% compared to the baseline configuration without cavities and end-wall contouring.

HB simulations offer substantial savings in computational effort. For example, the HB setup with steady cavities requires only 271.5 normalized CPU hours, compared to over 8000 hours for the full TD simulation. Even the HB configuration with unsteady cavity modeling, initialized from the steady HB solution, remains significantly more efficient than TD, despite requiring nearly double the CPU hours due to reduced CFL numbers and

slower convergence behavior.

The increased computational cost observed for the HB method with unsteady cavities is primarily associated with challenges during the initialization phase. Nevertheless, significant reductions in runtime are expected to be achievable through improved initialization strategies and the adoption of more robust solver settings, which would enhance stability and accelerate convergence.

5 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

This study investigates the influence of secondary air-seal cavities and unsteady flow modeling on the aerodynamic performance of a large-scale, multi-stage low-pressure turbine representative of industrial applications. The results highlight several key findings.

Secondary cavities have a pronounced impact on the flow field, particularly in the rear stages where they alter the radial distribution of thermal loads. Neglecting these features leads to significant deviations in total temperature, up to 8 K near the shroud and around 2 K near the hub, underscoring the importance of including cavity effects in high-fidelity CFD simulations.

Steady-state simulations systematically underpredict radial mixing, especially at mid-span. In contrast, unsteady approaches capture wake transport and vortex interactions that are inherently suppressed by the mixing plane method, leading to more accurate predictions of time-averaged radial distributions and integral performance values such as isentropic efficiency.

The HB method demonstrates excellent agreement with TD simulations for both global performance metrics and local unsteady pressure amplitudes. Minor discrepancies appear near the endwalls and trailing edge regions due to the limited frequency content prescribed in the HB setup.

Unsteady pressure excitation analysis revealed peak am-

TABLE 2: NUMERICAL PERFORMANCE, MESH SIZE AND CPU HOURS.

Setup	Cells _{nrm}	CPUh _{nrm}
RANS, woCav	1.0	1.0
URANS-TD, woCav	32.5	4387.4
RANS	1.7	5.6
URANS-HB, steadyCav	1.7	271.5
URANS-HB	1.7	453.7*
URANS-TD	56.1	8174.3

* initialized from HB solution with steady cavities

FIGURE 5: PRESSURE AMPLITUDE DISTRIBUTION AT THE VANE PASSING FREQUENCY OF STATOR 2 ON THE SUCTION AND PRESSURE SIDES OF BLADE 2: (a) URANS-TD WITHOUT CAVITIES, (b) URANS-HB WITH STEADY CAVITIES, (c) URANS-HB WITH UNSTEADY CAVITIES AND (d) URANS-TD.

FIGURE 6: PRESSURE AMPLITUDES ON BLADE 2 AT 50% AND 95% CHANNEL HEIGHT.

plitudes at the vane passing frequency near the leading edge (20–30% span) and blade tip. These amplitudes were influenced by cavity geometry, particularly near the endwalls.

In the presented configuration, modeling unsteady flow inside the cavities within HB did not significantly affect global performance metrics or time-averaged radial distributions in the

main flow path. While some influence on pressure amplitudes near the shroud was observed, the overall distribution remained qualitatively unchanged.

From a computational perspective, HB simulations require only a single passage per blade row, resulting in a mesh size approximately 33 times smaller than the 180° TD model. In terms

of CPU hours, HB consumes only 3.3% of the resources needed for TD simulations and offers faster pre- and post-processing. This makes HB a highly attractive method for industrial design processes where turnaround time and resource efficiency are critical. Although the presented configuration allows TD simulations on a 180° sector, the advantages of HB become even more significant for configurations that require full-annulus (360°) modeling in TD. In such cases, the ability of HB to operate on a single-passage model drastically reduces computational cost while still capturing the dominant unsteady interactions, making it particularly suitable for large multi-stage turbines or cases with strong circumferential asymmetries.

Although TD simulations remain the reference for capturing complex frequency interactions such as clocking and indexing effects, especially in large multi-stage configurations, HB proves to be an efficient alternative. Its ability to reproduce key unsteady phenomena with drastically reduced computational cost makes it a valuable tool for high-fidelity turbine analysis.

Future work will focus on extending the analysis to aerodynamic forces and work exchange in the context of aeroelasticity, as required for forced response assessments.

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